

ORGANIC AGRICULTURE PRODUCTION: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICES (KAP) OF THE BENEFICIARIES FROM BARANGAY SITOG, KATIPUNAN, ZDN

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Abstract

The coconut industry is a cornerstone of the Philippine economy, employing millions of farmers and providing a major source of income. However, coconut farmers in Zamboanga del Norte face significant challenges, making it essential to explore alternative income sources, such as organic agriculture. The Organic Agriculture Production Extension Project, implemented by the College of Agriculture and Forestry, aimed to enhance knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of coconut farmers in Barangay Sitog regarding organic agriculture. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to evaluate the project's effectiveness among 64 coconut farmers. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and questionnaires translated into the Cebuano dialect. Results revealed that farmers possessed high levels of knowledge and favorable attitudes towards organic agriculture; however, practical adoption varied. Despite positive attitudes and understanding of organic methods, the translation into consistent practices was hindered by economic challenges, limited access to organic inputs, and logistical barriers. Spearman's Rank Order Correlation showed that educational attainment and income positively influenced knowledge but had minimal impact on practical application. The study concludes that while the project effectively enhanced awareness, further targeted interventions are needed to bridge the gap between knowledge and practice. Recommendations include enhanced hands-on training, resource subsidies, establishing farmer cooperatives, and policy incentives. Emphasis is placed on providing accessible organic farming resources, strengthening farmer networks, and continuous project evaluation. Integrating organic farming into school curricula is also suggested to ensure long-term adoption and community resilience. These measures aim to create a supportive environment that fosters sustainable agricultural practices among coconut farmers.

Keywords: Coconut Industry, Organic Agriculture, Knowledge-Attitude-Practice, Extension Project, Sustainable Farming Practices.

INTRODUCTION

The coconut industry is vital for the Philippine economy, being the country's most significant agricultural land and labor employer. Due to its significant contribution to the economy and as a primary source of income, coconut is considered an indicator of the country's overall economic activity (Clarete & Roumasset, 1983). The industry employs approximately 3 million coconut farmers and employees, along with 25 million Filipinos working in other coconut-based enterprises nationwide (PCA, 2019).

Most farmers in the Zamboanga Peninsula make a living by cultivating coconut palms. According to the 2008 census, coconuts are grown on approximately 368,365 hectares in Zamboanga del Norte, Zamboanga del Sur, Sibugay, and Zamboanga City (Usman, 2015).

Zamboanga del Norte boasts an extensive land area dedicated to coconut cultivation, spanning 208,370 square kilometers. From 2011 to 2015, it contributed 784,076 metric tons to the region's coconut production, 47% of 1,682,120 metric tons (PCA, 2017).

According to Penalis (2022), banana plantation and vegetable gardening were standard alternative livelihood options for coconut farmers in the municipalities of La Libertad, Piñan, Rizal, and Sibutad in Zamboanga del Norte. Despite this, these farmers faced significant challenges in crop production, poultry, swine, and cattle raising. As a result, many of them recognized the importance of diversifying their income beyond coconut farming.

Organic agriculture as an alternative source of farmers might be one of the community's options for dealing with food insecurity and providing families with mental stability. Historical examples from tough times demonstrate how crucial organic farming may be in our society. The best and most feasible way to save costs while safeguarding farmers' income and health is to use organic inputs and methods. JRMSU-KC's College of Agriculture and Forestry carried out an extension project to assist beneficiaries, particularly coconut producers, and the community in increasing their agricultural ability while adopting organic agriculture production practices. The project was conducted to educate participants on the benefits of growing and producing organic products, as well as the Organic Act of 2010, which, among other things, establishes and promotes organic agriculture in the Philippines under Republic Act 10068. Section 2 declares the State's policy to promote, propagate, further develop, and implement organic agriculture in the Philippines, which will cumulatively condition and enrich soil fertility, increase farm productivity, reduce pollution and environmental destruction, prevent natural resource depletion, protect the health of farmers, consumers, and the general public, and save on imported farm inputs.

To that end, a comprehensive project was launched to promote community-based organic agriculture systems. This includes farmer-produced purely organic fertilizers such as compost, pesticides, vermicomposting, and other farm inputs, as well as a nationwide educational and promotional campaign for their use and processing and the adoption of the organic agricultural system as a viable alternative source of income for the beneficiaries.

Furthermore, Section 3b defines organic agriculture as any agricultural system that promotes ecologically sound, socially acceptable, financially viable, and technically feasible food and fiber production. Organic agriculture reduces external inputs by not utilizing chemical fertilizers, pesticides, or pharmaceuticals. It also includes but is not limited to soil fertility management, varietal breeding and selection under chemical and pesticide-free conditions, the use of biotechnology, and other cultural practices that are consistent with the principles and policies of this Act and increase productivity without destroying the soil or harming farmers, consumers, or the environment, as defined by the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movement (IFOAM, 2006).

According to the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM) global data from 2015, the Philippines ranked fifth on the list of countries with the most organic producers, with over 165,958, and eighth on the list of countries with the most hectares of

organic land, with over 234,642 hectares, ranking fourth in Asia (Arcalas et al., 2019). Hence, the activity aided organic agriculture enthusiasts and gave them courage and a voice to press for organic practices in the country's agriculture field.

The Community Extension Project, which was carried out in collaboration with the coconut farmers' association, the College of Agriculture and Forestry, and the School of Engineering at Jose Rizal Memorial State University-Katipunan Campus, encompassed one barangay in Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, known as Sitog. Barangay Sitog was selected from other barangays in the Municipality of Katipunan because of its extensive coconut plantations, and they are known for their active participation in agricultural projects conducted by the Department of Agriculture. Seventy-seven (77) participants were catered to and taught how to produce organic concoctions for fertilizer, insecticide, livestock feed, soil bed, and seed preparation. The completed project also included raising organic chickens, producing organic vegetables, establishing vermicomposting, and discussing the importance of organic agriculture through an environmental management system that teaches our beneficiaries how to conserve and preserve our natural resources. This workshop aimed to examine and certify coconut farmers' abilities to ensure production, quality, and global competitiveness. It was also used to assess a person's certification level and, if they had competency gaps, to determine their training requirements.

The College of Agriculture and Forestry conducted the Organic Agriculture Production to Coconut Farmers' Association at Barangay Sitog with the aims of establishing and introducing the materials for producing organic vegetables, fertilizer, pesticides, and feeds as well as vermicomposting to the participants, beneficiaries can demonstrate skills in producing and harvesting organic vegetables, fertilizers, concoctions, and feeds as well as vermicomposting, guiding and facilitating the trainees in the proper application of organic fertilizers and concoctions to crops and farm animals, and uplifting trainees to become productive by utilizing available resources in the community and process it into organic inputs as their alternative source of income and for their consumption and business.

Significance of the study

The survey was essential in assessing coconut farmers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding the College of Agriculture and Forestry's extension initiative. It also served as a foundation for the institution to improve its extension services and assess the project's success. The efficacy of the Organic Agriculture Production Extension Project must be evaluated to see how it helped Barangay Sitog's coconut farmers in terms of knowledge, attitudes, and practices.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The scope of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of the Organic Agriculture Production Extension Project among the coconut farmers in Barangay Sitog, Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte. However, the study had certain limitations. Out of the 77 beneficiaries of the extension project, only 64 were interviewed. This reduction was due to unavoidable circumstances, such as the death of some beneficiaries and the migration of others to different locations for work-

related reasons. Consequently, the findings may not fully represent the perspectives of all beneficiaries, which may affect the generalizability of the results. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the majority of the participants and highlights areas for further intervention to promote sustainable organic farming.

Objectives

Generally, the study evaluates the effectiveness of the Organic Agriculture Production Extension Project of the College of Agriculture and Forestry to the Coconut Farmers of Barangay Sitog, Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte.

Specifically, this evaluation of the extension project aims to:

1. Determine the level of knowledge of the beneficiaries of the extension project conducted by the College of Agriculture and Forestry.
2. Assess the beneficiaries' attitude level after the College conducted the extension project.
3. Identify to what extent farmers practice organic farming.
4. Assess the relationships between selected personal characteristics of the farmers (age, educational attainment, farming experience, organic farming experience, coconut farm size, monthly family income) and the knowledge, attitude, and practice of organic farming.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The coconut is often referred to as the "tree of life" due to its diverse range of products, including water, flower sap, cream, milk, and cooking oil from the kernel, as well as geotextiles and organic fertilizer from the husk, activated carbon and fashion accessories from the shell, and baskets and brooms from the leaves. More recently, it has also been utilized for medicinal, cosmeceutical, and nutraceutical products and biofuel from the oil. In the Philippines, coconut exports generate around US\$1 billion annually, and approximately one-third of the population depends on coconuts for their livelihood. However, despite its economic importance, coconut farmers are often marginalized, with many living below the poverty line. This highlights that the full potential of the coconut has not been realized to the extent that it could significantly improve the lives of coconut farmers. Over 90 percent of coconut farmers are smallholders, managing 4 hectares of land or less. Many work on land they do not own, making them ineligible for formal banking services and lacking the influence to shape government or private sector policies. Poverty prevents these farmers from investing in their aging coconut farms, leading to declining yields and exports. Without sustainable efforts to address poverty in coconut-growing communities, the situation will continue to deteriorate (Batugal P. et al., 2012).

Production in organic farming is a system founded on the idea of preserving nature while taking into account all living forms. The industry is developing in the Philippines and primarily in the United States, Europe, and other Asian nations. Although this farming method is cost-effective and healthy, it does not use toxic and expensive synthetic chemicals (Porciuncula et al., 2015).

Consumers' concerns about food safety, quality, and environmental preservation were the first to drive demand for organic products, which fueled the growth of organic agriculture, especially in developed nations. In response, governments have established goals for the growth of organic farming, and as part of their plan to allay these worries, new market opportunities have been created (POARM, 2007). Furthermore, there is no question growing organic vegetables has positive ecological effects and is consistent with the Philippine government's policy of advancing citizens' rights to a healthy, balanced ecosystem that is in harmony with the cycles and rhythms of nature (Article II, Sec. 6, Philippine Constitution).

Consumer interest in preserving production procedures for fresh fruits and vegetables, particularly for certified organic crops, has increased due to growing sales of organic commodities, dietary changes, serious worries about food safety, and increased awareness of one's health. Numerous years of research on organic farms have shown traits of sustainable farming, including decreased soil erosion, decreased use of fossil fuels, decreased nitrate leaching, increased carbon sequestration, and little to no pesticide usage (Kuepper et al., 2004).

Extension services bridge scientific information and practical implementation, guiding farmers when they need to switch to more sustainable practices. Because organic farming prioritizes soil health and biodiversity more than synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, it presents unique opportunities and challenges (Joshi & Narayan et al., 2019).

Extension services provide comprehensive support to grape growers in areas such as agricultural practices, marketing operations, and compliance with quality standards, ultimately aiming to increase their income and export competitiveness (Nikam et al. et al., 2016). The role of extension services in the paper includes facilitating the transfer of agricultural technologies, promoting the adoption of new technologies, bringing about changes through education and communication, disseminating information, building the capacity of farmers, providing sustainable agricultural education, and organizing the dissemination of agricultural information through various channels (Ali et al. et al., 2012). The role of extension services in agriculture is pivotal in bridging the gap between research, innovation, and practical implementation on the farm. Extension services act as a crucial link, facilitating the transfer of knowledge, technologies, and best practices from research institutions to farmers, thereby contributing to the overall development of the agricultural sector. This note explores the multifaceted role of extension services and their impact on farmers, agricultural productivity, and rural communities.

Furthermore, according to the study of Juyal et al. (2022), the effectiveness of extension services in organic farming is an essential component in the successful acceptance and long-term application of organic practices. Extension services are crucial in raising awareness, distributing vital knowledge, and encouraging the adoption of environmentally friendly and sustainable agricultural practices. Extension programs help farmers learn organic farming methods. Extension agents are essential in providing farmers with the knowledge and skills they need to transition to organic methods through targeted training programs, workshops, and one-on-one consultations. Extension services provide specialized guidance assistance for farmers, addressing the challenges and possibilities they experience when adopting and

sustaining organic agricultural techniques. Farmers who get continuous and focused instruction are more likely to apply sustainable practices, follow organic certification criteria, and reap the advantages, such as better soil health and less environmental impact. Investment in training programs, contemporary communication methods, and recruiting and retaining experienced extension people are critical for overcoming these obstacles and ensuring that extension services stay relevant and responsive to organic farmers' changing requirements.

As per the findings of Pastor et al. (2011), the primary reasons for the non-adoption or discontinuation of organic farming include labor-intensive and time-consuming practices, slow results, inadequate government support, lower yields, and income, lack of technical knowledge and assistance, and pest-related issues. Given these insights, it is evident that targeted promotional efforts could be beneficial if the government is genuinely committed to promoting organic farming within the country. For example, some farmers may have limited technical knowledge about organic farming, which could impact their understanding of its benefits. To address this, it would be beneficial to intensify information, education, and communication (IEC) efforts to educate them about the long-term and significant contributions of organic farming. This could help cultivate a more positive attitude towards organic farming among farmers. Additionally, sharing research results and documenting the sustainable benefits of organic farming or organizing research and off-farm demonstrations could provide valuable support. Furthermore, it is essential to meet farmers' demands for support in adopting organic practices, and the government should find ways to fulfill and extend these needs.

Organic farming continues to spearhead the movement towards social, economic, and environmental sustainability. Research suggests that the growth of this sector has brought about positive outcomes for counties with both organic and conventional farms, as opposed to those with solely conventional farms. These findings support the rationale for government initiatives to promote the expansion of organic agriculture in the United States (Lohr, L., 2011).

Numerous factors may explain the transition to organic farming (OF), and these factors influence conversion decisions through a wide range of motivations, extending beyond purely economic reasons. The decision to convert is influenced by attitudes and opinions, which are not always readily observable. Incorporating these variables as explanatory factors in econometric models may present methodological challenges (such as endogeneity).

Additionally, the specific contexts in which farmers operate influence how motivations and various observable factors impact their decisions, limiting the generalizability of results across countries, regions, and periods. The factors influencing conversion rates often vary based on the specific region or territory and the production type. Few observable variables, such as age and education, impact different farming types or regions.

Therefore, it is crucial to conduct comparative studies using counterfactual methods and econometric research to understand the effect of conversion on agricultural employment and farm profitability and the role of technical efficiency in the decision to convert. Additionally, it is essential to consider the spatial distribution of farmers, including the effects of neighborhood and market localization.

Consequently, research teams should gather comprehensive and consistent databases for conventional and organic farms. Building networks of teams in these fields will facilitate the integration of specific information about organic farming in agricultural inventories (Geniaux G. et al., 2011).

According to Mondal S. et al. (2014), farmers should receive skill-based training in organic vegetable production principles. They should also be provided with accurate information on pest management systems from developed countries, trained in organic matter management and compost production, assisted in forming cooperative groups to share knowledge, and made aware of the benefits of adopting positive attitudes. Moreover, they should be informed that organic vegetable farming leads to favorable market prices.

The age of farmers had a significant and negative impact on organic farming. In contrast, the experience of farmers had a positive and significant effect on the attitudes of the respondent sample population towards organic agriculture. The correlation between environmental and cost-benefit aspects with the age factor of farmers indicated a damaging relationship for farmers involved in organic crop production. On the other hand, the experience of respondent farmers was positively correlated with the environmental and cost-benefit aspects of organic production. It was recommended that relevant governmental and non-governmental organizations and provincial departments collaborate to assist smallholder farmers in natural farming. Areas in which smallholders can collaborate include acquiring the knowledge and skills required to produce vegetables, crops, and livestock using organic farming. It is crucial to address the general and specific conditions influencing smallholder farmers' attitudes toward organic agriculture and its impact on the environment and economic benefits (Kidane et al., 2022).

Organic food production has both environmental and economic benefits. However, farmers' knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) about organic farming have not been evaluated. Das et al. (2019) previously performed a KAP survey on nitrogen-fortified organic manure production and crop cultivation. Nair and Ravindran (2015) published another survey study on using chlorpyrifos and paraquat and their influence on human health and the environment, also known as inorganic agricultural practice. A KAP survey was also performed on climate change (Severin & Small, 2016). Ntawuruhunga (2016) investigated African farmers' KAP for Indigenous vegetable production in Kenya. According to the research (Launiala, 2009), the KAP survey's appeal stems from its simple design, quantifiable data, ease of interpretation and concise presentation of results, generalizability of small-sample results to a larger population, cross-cultural comparability, speed of implementation, and ease of training enumerators.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study draws on several key concepts from recent literature. Pongcharoen, K. (2020) emphasizes the importance of understanding the barriers and motivations that influence farmers' adoption of organic practices. They highlight that while many farmers are motivated by the environmental and health benefits of organic farming, they

often face significant barriers, such as a lack of knowledge and access to resources. Similarly, Joshi and Narayan (2019) underscore the critical role of extension services in promoting sustainable agricultural practices, noting that effective training and support can significantly enhance farmers' knowledge and attitudes towards organic farming.

Moreover, the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) model provides a robust framework for assessing the impact of organic agriculture initiatives at the community level. Ntawuruhunga (2016) and Mondal and Chattopadhyay (2014) have demonstrated the utility of the KAP model in evaluating farmers' understanding and implementation of organic farming techniques. Their studies indicate that a positive attitude towards organic farming and adequate knowledge and training can lead to better adoption and practice of organic methods. This framework is particularly relevant for analyzing the beneficiaries in Barangay Sitog, Katipunan, and Zamboanga del Norte, as it helps to identify specific areas where knowledge and attitudes can be improved to enhance organic farming practices. By leveraging insights from these studies, this research aims to develop targeted interventions that can address the unique challenges faced by local farmers and promote sustainable agricultural development in the region.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of organic agriculture production: evaluating the effectiveness of the extension project of the College of Agriculture and Forestry at Barangay Sitog, Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte

METHODOLOGY

Research design and Data collection

A descriptive-correlational method of research was used to conduct the study. This type of

research collects information describing the respondent and program-related factors and determines the type and degree of relationships among the study's key variables (Aguanta, L. M., & Intong, J. D., 2016). The target population of the study was the members of the Coconut Farmers' Association in Barangay Sitog, Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, who were the beneficiaries of the OAP extension project conducted by the College of Agriculture and Forestry of JRMSU-Katipunan Campus. A complete list of the attendees from the project will be obtained from the Extension Office of the College of Agriculture and Forestry to determine the 64 coconut farmers.

Figure 2: Map of the Municipality of Katipunan where Barangay Sitog is located

Research Instrument

Preparation and validation of the guide questions and questionnaire

a. Questionnaire

A questionnaire was used to gather data. According to Jones et al. (2013), questionnaires allow researchers to gather large amounts of data quickly and efficiently.

This method is particularly effective for addressing numerous issues in a systematic way and for obtaining sensitive information. Additionally, it is valuable for obtaining statistical data on the perspectives of a specific group of individuals.

A brief review of the questionnaire was conducted to ensure that all necessary information was obtained during the assessment. It was also translated into the Cebuano dialect to make it easier for the respondents to understand.

b. Pilot Testing

The researcher made the questionnaire. The objectives were lifted from the program's operational scheme. The level of knowledge, attitude, and practice will be obtained. Pilot testing was conducted to ensure the instrument's reliability and validity. A rate of .731 validity and reliability using the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient in the SPSS v 16 statistical tool indicates an acceptable level of reliability, suggesting that the items on the scale are sufficiently consistent in measuring the intended construct. It was a small-scale study undertaken in preparation for conducting survey research and used to determine the reliability or internal consistency of a set of scale or test items. This will be done to 30 non-respondents before the surveys' implementation.

Data gathering procedure

a. Ethical consideration

During the survey, the researcher requested permission from the respondents to be surveyed and assured them that their beliefs would be respected. They were also informed that the names they provide will be kept secret.

b. Semi-structured interviews

The researcher conducted informal interviews with the coconut farmers using a semi-structured questionnaire. Respondents were visited in their areas, and others were gathered in an open space or covered court for interviews.

c. Conduct of the survey

A face-to-face interview with beneficiaries was done. Interviews were conducted in restricted cases so as not to disrupt beneficiaries as they work on their farms. The findings were presented through a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with various stakeholders, including the Coconut Farmers' Association officials, the Barangay Chairman, and the Barangay Agriculture Officer.

Elimination of Potential Bias

The project adopted several strategies to eliminate potential bias in the evaluation process. Clear criteria and standardization ensured uniform assessments, with detailed data collection and analysis guidelines to minimize subjective interpretation. Pilot testing survey questionnaires and training were refined tools for accuracy and appropriateness.

Engaging diverse stakeholder's balances biases and provides a holistic view. Thoroughly trained and calibrated enumerators reduce personal biases. Blind data analysis with anonymized data ensures unbiased analysis.

An independent in-house review adds objectivity. Multiple data sources and triangulation methods validate findings and reduce reliance on a single source. These strategies aim to ensure a robust, objective, and reliable evaluation of the impact of extension services on organic coconut farming practices.

Data processing and analysis

After completion of the survey, all interview schedules were collated for data processing. The qualitative data were transformed into the quantitative form using appropriate codes and scores whenever required. In many cases, indices and scales were created by simply adding scores assigned to people or patterns of qualities. Indices and scales were considered the most efficient data reduction and analysis tools.

Following Nishi et al. (2019), six selected farmer characteristics were handled as independent variables in this study. The criteria include age, educational qualification, farming experience, organic farming experience, farm size, and monthly family income. The study focuses on knowledge, attitude, and practice of organic farming.

Measurement of focus issues

a. Knowledge

The interview schedule comprises ten (10) questions designed to assess farmers' agricultural expertise. All of the questions focus on Bloom's taxonomy's "cognitive domain (knowledge)" (Bloom et al., 1956). Regardless of the complexity of the answer, a score of 1 will be assigned to each question. (For a correct answer against each question, the respondent would score 1; if an incorrect answer, it would be 0). Thus, the total score for the question was 10. Farmers will receive marks based on the accuracy of their answers.

A farmer's overall score was calculated by adding points for ten (10) questions. A farmer's understanding of organic farming can vary from 10, with 0 indicating low knowledge and 10 indicating extensive knowledge. Farmers were divided into three categories depending on their agricultural knowledge score: low knowledge (1-4), medium knowledge (5-8), and high knowledge (9-10).

b. Attitude

To assess farmers' attitudes toward organic farming, 20 statements (10 positive and 10 negative) were included in the interview schedule. A five-point Likert-type scale (strongly agree, agree, uncertain, disagree, strongly disagree) was used for each statement, weighing 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

The negative remarks were weighed in reverse. A farmer's attitude toward organic farming scored on a scale of 20 to 100, with 20 being the least positive attitude and 100 representing the most favorable. The attitude scores of a farmer were calculated by adding all of the scores against the twenty (20) statements. Farmers were divided into three groups based on their attitude scores: Less favorable (20-45), Moderately favorable (46-60), and highly favorable attitudes (>61) (Islam, M. S., & Islam, M. M., 2020).

c. Practice

Several agricultural activities served as indications of organic farming activity. However, only ten (10) practice statements (developed in consultation with academicians and extension agents) were included in the interview schedule to assess farmers' organic agricultural

practices. Each farmer was asked to rate the extent of his or her practice on a four-point scale of regularly, sometimes, seldom, and not at all for each statement, with weights of 3, 2, 1, and 0 assigned to these rating scales, respectively.

A farmer's practice scores were calculated by adding up all of his or her scores for the ten (10) practices that he or she practiced. The practice score could range from 0-30, where 0 indicates no practice and 30 indicates the highest extent of practice. Farmers were divided into three categories depending on their practice scores: Low (1-10), Medium (11-20), and High practice (21-30), according to the research study by Islam, M.S. et al. (2020). To compare the specific statements connected to the practice of organic farming, the following formula was used (modified from Hanif et al. (2020)):

$TPS = (N1 \times 3) + (N2 \times 2) + (N3 \times 1) + 0(1)$, where TPS = Total Practice Score, N1 = the number of farmers who practiced frequently, N2 = the number of farmers who practiced occasionally, N3 = the number of farmers who practiced seldom, and N4 = the number of farmers who practiced never. Individual practice scores can vary from "0 - 192" ($0 \times 64 = 0$ to $3 \times 64 = 192$), with 0 representing no practice and 192 indicating the highest level of practice. The extent of each practice (Practice Index) estimated using the following formula (Das et al., 2019):

$$PI = \frac{PSO}{PSH}$$

where PI = Practice Index, PSO = observed practice score, and PSH = possible highest score. The Ten selected practices were ranked based on the Practice Index (PI). The technique outlined by Sheel et al. (2019) was followed to calculate and measure the chosen attributes: age, educational attainment, farming experience, organic farming experience, farm size, and monthly family income.

d. Statistical tools and techniques used

Following collection, the data was evaluated and tabulated for interpretation. The data was interpreted using statistical treatments such as number, mean, standard deviation, rank order, etc. Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (ρ) analyzes the relationship between two variables (for ordinal data). Data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 indicates that coconut farmers demonstrate substantial levels of knowledge, favorable attitudes, and moderate to high levels of practice in relation to the subject matter, underscoring a generally positive orientation toward both understanding and engagement. Knowledge scores ranged from 4 to 10, with an overwhelming majority (76%) categorized in the high knowledge group (scoring between 9 and 10).

This high knowledge level is further evidenced by a mean score of 8.5 ± 1.47 , suggesting that the respondent pool is well-informed and potentially familiar with advanced concepts within the topic. The minimal representation in the low knowledge category (2%) implies that knowledge gaps are rare, signifying a baseline competence or higher across the group.

Attitude scores, spanning from 52 to 68, further reinforce this positive orientation. A significant 77% of coconut farmers were classified in the high attitude category (scores ≥ 61), with a mean score of 63.5 ± 3.76 . Notably, no respondents scored in the “less” attitude category, which indicates an absence of negative or indifferent views within the group. This high attitude score suggests a strong alignment between respondents' beliefs and the subject matter, likely enhancing both receptivity to and enthusiasm for engaging further with related practices. This positive attitudinal stance could serve as a motivating factor in sustaining or enhancing practical application, as attitudes often underpin behavioral intentions.

The results for practice, with scores ranging from 13 to 27, exhibit more variability. Although 44% of coconut farmers fall within the high practice category (scores ≥ 20), the majority (52%) are positioned in the medium practice range (11-20), leading to a mean practice score of 19.2 ± 5.36 . This distribution suggests that while a substantial number of respondents actively engage in applying their knowledge, some practical constraints may exist that inhibit higher levels of application across the board. Factors such as resource availability, logistical barriers, or varying levels of confidence in practice execution may contribute to this spread. The presence of a small percentage (4%) in the low-practice category indicates that a minority of respondents may require additional support or resources to reach medium or high levels of practical engagement.

Overall, the data in table 1 portrays a respondent group characterized by robust knowledge and positive attitudes, with a commendable, though varied, level of practical application. While the alignment between knowledge and attitude appears strong, the broader practice range suggests potential areas for targeted intervention, such as training or resource allocation, to bolster practical engagement uniformly. These findings imply that respondents are both informed and motivated, creating a promising foundation for initiatives to enhance applied practice across the group.

Recent studies on knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) in various contexts provide insights into public understanding and behavior. In agriculture, Thai farmers showed varying levels of sustainable practice adoption influenced by socio-environmental factors and perceptions (Liao et al., 2022). Similarly, Indonesian farmers demonstrated high knowledge of good agricultural practices for pesticide usage, but implementation was inconsistent (Dewi et al., 2022). During the COVID-19 pandemic, a Saudi Arabian study revealed high levels of knowledge, optimistic attitudes, and good practices among the public, with gender and age differences noted (Al-Hanawi et al., 2020). A mixed-method study across Southeast and South Asia found varying KAP prevalence rates, with South Asia generally scoring higher than Southeast Asia (Rahman et al., 2022). These studies consistently highlight the importance of knowledge in shaping attitudes and practices, while also identifying demographic factors that influence KAP outcomes across different domains.

Table 1: The distribution of respondents is based on their knowledge, attitudes, and practices in organic farming

Characteristics	Range	Categories and Scores	Respondents		Mean±SD
			Number	Percentage	
Knowledge	4-10	Low (1-4)	1	2%	8.5±1.47
		Medium (5-8)	14	22%	
		High (9-10)	49	76%	
Attitude	52-68	Less (20-45)	0	0%	63.5±3.76
		Moderately (46-60)	15	23%	
		High (≥61)	49	77%	
Practice	13-27	Low (1-10)	3	4%	19.2±5.36
		Medium (11-20)	33	52%	
		High (≥20)	28	44%	

Extent Organic Farming Methods

The table 2 data on the extent of organic farming methods practiced by respondents reveals a diverse range of practices that vary significantly in terms of frequency and adoption. Each farming method's total practice score (TPS) and practice index (PI) percentages were calculated to provide insight into the prevalence of these methods, while rank order helps clarify relative adoption levels across the farming community. The highest-ranked practice, with a TPS of 162 and a PI of 84.38%, is the ability to grow different crops on the same site. This suggests a high degree of crop diversification, which is often encouraged in organic farming to improve soil health and manage pests. Closely following this, ranked second, is the appropriate management of crop rotation and cultivation schedules, which had a TPS of 161 and a PI of 83.85%. This further indicates the respondents' commitment to sustainable agricultural practices that foster soil nutrient balance and productivity. The third most frequently adopted method was leaving the cultivable field fallow before further cultivation, with a TPS of 149 and a PI of 77.60%. This practice allows soil nutrients to regenerate naturally, enhancing soil fertility. Tillage before manure application ranked fourth, with a TPS of 146 and a PI of 76.04%. The tillage practice signifies farmers' awareness of preparing the soil to optimize the effectiveness of manure as a nutrient source. Similarly, the act of watering the field as needed ranked fifth (TPS of 141, PI of 73.44%), demonstrating the farmers' attention to crop irrigation management for optimal growth. On the other hand, practices such as applying cow and poultry manure every season ranked sixth (TPS of 133, PI of 69.27%), and the use of organic pesticides in addition to manure was ranked seventh (TPS of 115, PI of 59.90%). This implies that while these are important organic methods, they are somewhat less frequently applied, which could be due to the additional labor or costs involved in such practices. Managing pests and insects through innovative organic technological approaches was ranked eighth (TPS of 100, PI of 52.08%), indicating moderate adoption levels. This suggests that although organic pest management is practiced, it may present challenges to farmers in terms of accessibility or practicality. The treatment of animals with manure supplements ranked ninth, with a TPS of 80 and a PI of 41.67%, reflecting a lower extent of practice. This may indicate that livestock management practices are less integrated into the overall organic farming systems of the respondents. Finally, the least adopted practice was the consistent analysis of soil, ranked tenth (TPS of 44,

PI of 22.92%). This reveals that soil testing is largely overlooked by farmers, potentially due to cost, lack of access to testing facilities, or limited knowledge of the benefits of soil analysis. Overall, the data indicates a notable emphasis on crop diversification and rotation, with these practices being the most extensively adopted. Conversely, soil analysis is an underutilized practice, indicating a potential area for capacity-building initiatives aimed at promoting the benefits of soil health assessment in improving crop productivity. Furthermore, the moderate adoption of organic pesticides and manure applications highlights the opportunity for increased advocacy and support in the form of training and resources for sustainable organic farming practices.

Previous researches support this claim that crop diversification and rotation are widely adopted practices, while soil analysis remains underutilized (Rietra et al., 2022). Organic management significantly improves soil health (+47%) but results in lower yields (-34%) compared to conventional systems (Walder et al., 2023). Crop diversity, perennials in rotation, tillage, and manure use influence soil biochemical health indicators in organic corn fields (Sprunger et al., 2021). However, organic farmers face persistent barriers to adopting diversification practices, including high land rents, short-term leases, and stringent food safety standards (Carlisle et al., 2022). To overcome these challenges and achieve multifunctional agroecosystems, a combination of crop diversification, organic amendments, and effective crop protection is recommended. Integrating conventional and alternative approaches could help balance production and soil health, leading to more sustainable and productive agricultural systems (Walder et al., 2023).

Table 2: The extent of organic farming methods in ranked order

Statements	Extent of Practice				TPS	PI (%)	Rank
	Regularly (3)	Sometimes (2)	Seldom (1)	Not at all (0)			
1. Every season, I apply cow and poultry manure around the field.	3 x 17	2 x 40	1 x 2	0 x 5	133	69.27%	6 th
2. Tillage is completed before manure application.	3 x 33	2 x 22	1 x 3	0 x 6	146	76.04%	4 th
3. Soil is analyzed consistently.	3 x 8	2 x 8	1 x 4	0 x 44	44	22.92%	10 th
4. Organic pesticides were utilized in addition to manure.	3 x 19	2 x 26	1 x 6	0 x 13	115	59.90%	7 th
5. Animals are treated with manure supplements.	3 x 13	2 x 17	1 x 7	0 x 27	80	41.67%	9 th
6. Pests and insects were also managed utilizing an innovative organic technological approach.	3 x 14	2 x 25	1 x 8	0 x 17	100	52.08%	8 th
7. Before further cultivation, the cultivable field was left fallow.	3 x 35	2 x 20	1 x 4	0 x 5	149	77.60%	3 rd
8. I water my field as much as necessary.	3 x 31	2 x 21	1 x 6	0 x 6	141	73.44%	5 th
9. Crop rotation and cultivation schedules are appropriately managed.	3 x 35	2 x 28	1 x 0	0 x 1	161	83.85%	2 nd
10. I can simply grow different crops on the same site.	3 x 41	2 x 17	1 x 5	0 x 1	162	84.38%	1 st

TPS = Total Practice Score, PI = Practice Index

Selected characteristics of the farmers

The data in table 3 presents the distribution of coconut farmers who are beneficiaries of the Organic Agriculture Production extension project, focusing on various socio-demographic and economic characteristics including age, educational attainment, farming experience, organic farming experience, farm size, and monthly income. This detailed examination highlights distinct trends that reflect the composition of the beneficiaries and their respective practices.

The majority of respondents fall within the older age group, with 58% aged above 50 years. This suggests that the organic agriculture project largely benefits more experienced and likely established farmers. Farmers in the middle age group (35-50 years) comprise 36% of respondents, while only 6% are categorized as young (under 35 years). This age distribution implies that the organic agriculture initiative has predominantly reached older individuals, possibly due to their greater land ownership or established role in farming communities. In terms of educational attainment, 47% of respondents have completed secondary education, making it the largest group, while 41% have only completed elementary education. Only 12% have attained tertiary education. This distribution suggests that most of the coconut farmers have limited formal education, which may have implications for their ability to access information or engage in training related to organic farming practices.

Regarding farming experience, 67% of the respondents have a high level of farming experience (over 20 years), reflecting that the majority are highly experienced farmers. Another 20% have medium experience (10-20 years), and 13% have less than 10 years of experience. This data highlights that the project participants are primarily seasoned farmers, which may be advantageous for the effective adoption of organic practices due to their accumulated knowledge and familiarity with agricultural processes. However, the respondents' organic farming experience shows a different pattern, with 75% having low experience (less than 5 years). Only 16% have medium experience (5-10 years), and a mere 9% have more than 10 years of organic farming experience. This discrepancy between general farming experience and specific organic farming experience suggests that while most farmers are experienced in traditional farming, they are relatively new to organic practices. This points to the need for ongoing training and capacity-building efforts to help these farmers transition successfully.

Farm size also shows significant variation, with 59% of the respondents classified as having medium-sized farms (1-2.99 hectares), indicating that medium-scale farming is most common among the beneficiaries. A smaller percentage (16%) have large farms (over 3 hectares), while 14% have marginal farms (0.02-0.50 hectares), and 3% have small farms (0.51-0.99 hectares). Interestingly, 8% of the respondents are classified as landless, suggesting that they may be cultivating land they do not own, which could have implications for their ability to fully invest in and benefit from organic farming practices. Income levels among the respondents indicate that 85% fall into the low-income category, earning less than 5,000 pesos per month. Only 9% earn between 5,001-10,000 pesos, and 6% earn more than 10,000 pesos per month. This income distribution suggests that the majority of the coconut farmers are economically vulnerable, which may affect their ability to adopt costly organic farming inputs or technologies.

In general, the data reflects that the beneficiaries of the organic agriculture extension project are predominantly older, experienced farmers with limited formal education and relatively low income. Their organic farming experience is minimal despite their general farming knowledge, indicating the need for targeted support and training to enhance their capability to adopt and benefit from organic agricultural practices effectively.

The research's result indicates that extension services play a crucial role in promoting organic agriculture adoption, though their effectiveness varies (Alotaibi et al., 2021). Factors influencing adoption include farmer characteristics (age, gender, education), psycho-behavioral aspects, farming experience, and supportive elements like training and information access (Sapbamrer, R. & Ajchamon Thammachai, 2021). Organic farmers often rely on peer networks and organizations for information rather than extension services. Challenges in organic farming include pest control, weed management, and weather-related issues (Alotaibi et al., 2021). Intensive training programs can effectively enhance farmers' knowledge, perceptions, and adoption of organic practices (M. Grimm & Nathalie Luck, 2023). To promote sustainable organic farming adoption, a collaborative approach involving extension agents, farm associations, and government support is recommended (Sapbamrer, R. & Ajchamon Thammachai, 2021).

Table 3: The distribution of respondents is based on their selected characteristics

Characteristics	Range	Categories and Scores	Respondents	
			Number	Percentage
Age (years)	15-80	Young (<35)	4	6%
		Middle (35-50)	23	36%
		Old (>50)	37	58%
Educational Attainment	0-3	Elementary	26	41%
		Secondary	30	47%
		Tertiary	8	12%
Farming experience (years)	1-50	Low (<10)	8	13%
		Medium (10-20)	13	20%
		High (>20)	43	67%
Organic Farming Experience (years)	1-50	Low (<5)	48	75%
		Medium (5-10)	10	16%
		High (>10)	6	9%
Farm size	0.2-6	Landless	5	8%
		Marginal (.02-.50)	9	14%
		Small (.51-.99)	2	3%
		Medium (1-2.99)	38	59%
		Large (>3)	10	16%
Monthly Income	0-20,000	Low (<5,000)	54	85%
		Medium (5001-10000)	6	9%
		High (>10,000)	4	6%

Relationship between KAP and Farmer's Characteristics

The computed Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient between the farmers' knowledge, attitude, and practices on organic farming and selected characteristics provides valuable insights into the potential factors influencing the adoption of organic agriculture. The

selected characteristics include age, educational attainment, farming experience, organic farming experience, farm size, and monthly income. The significance levels indicate the reliability of these relationships, with significance at the 5% level denoted by * and significance at the 1% level denoted by **.

The correlation between age and the farmers' knowledge, attitude, and practices on organic farming reveals weak and statistically insignificant relationships across all three dimensions. The correlation coefficient for knowledge (-0.072) suggests a slight negative association, implying that younger farmers may have slightly more knowledge about organic farming compared to older farmers. Conversely, the correlation with attitude (0.117) is weakly positive, indicating that older farmers might exhibit a marginally more favorable attitude towards organic farming. The coefficient for practice (-0.003) is almost zero, suggesting that age does not significantly influence the adoption of organic farming practices among respondents.

Educational attainment showed a significant positive correlation with knowledge ($\rho = 0.267$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that farmers with higher educational levels tend to have greater knowledge of organic farming. This finding emphasizes the role of formal education in enhancing awareness and understanding of organic farming practices. However, educational attainment has a weak and negative relationship with attitude (-0.134), indicating that higher education levels do not necessarily correlate with a more positive attitude towards organic farming. The correlation with practice (0.016) was also weak and not statistically significant, implying that higher educational attainment does not directly lead to greater implementation of organic farming practices.

Farming experience exhibited weak and statistically insignificant correlations with knowledge, attitude, and practice. The coefficients for farming experience were -0.042 for knowledge, -0.017 for attitude, and -0.037 for practice, indicating no meaningful association between general farming experience and the farmers' knowledge, attitudes, or practices related to organic farming. These results suggest that even experienced farmers may not necessarily have more knowledge or a stronger inclination towards organic farming, which highlights a gap in translating conventional farming experience into organic farming expertise.

Similarly, organic farming experience showed weak and non-significant relationships with knowledge, attitude, and practices. The correlation coefficients were 0.049 for knowledge, -0.011 for attitude, and 0.036 for practice. These findings indicate that the length of experience in organic farming does not have a significant impact on farmers' knowledge, attitudes, or adoption of organic practices. This suggests that merely having experience in organic farming may not be sufficient to foster increased knowledge or adoption of organic practices without targeted interventions or training.

The relationship between farm size and farmers' knowledge, attitude, and practices showed weak correlations. The negative coefficient for knowledge (-0.138) implies that farmers with smaller farms might possess slightly more knowledge about organic farming compared to those with larger farms.

The positive correlation with attitude (0.120) suggests that farmers with larger farms may exhibit a somewhat more favorable attitude towards organic farming, although this relationship is not statistically significant. The correlation with practice (-0.060) was also weak, indicating that farm size does not significantly affect the practical implementation of organic farming methods.

Monthly income showed a statistically significant positive correlation with knowledge ($\rho = 0.237$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that farmers with higher income levels tend to have greater knowledge of organic farming. This relationship suggests that economic stability may provide farmers with more opportunities to access information, training, or resources related to organic agriculture. However, the correlation between monthly income and attitude (-0.174) was negative and not significant, implying that higher income does not necessarily correlate with a more positive attitude towards organic farming.

The correlation between monthly income and practice (0.040) was weak and not significant, suggesting that income level does not have a substantial influence on the practical adoption of organic farming practices.

Overall, the data indicates that educational attainment and income are positively associated with farmers' knowledge of organic farming, highlighting the importance of education and economic stability in fostering awareness of organic practices. However, these characteristics do not appear to significantly influence attitudes or practices, suggesting that knowledge alone may not be enough to drive behavioral changes.

The weak correlations across most variables suggest the need for targeted interventions, such as training programs and support systems, to enhance farmers' attitudes and practices towards organic farming effectively. Bridging the gap between knowledge and practice remains crucial for the successful adoption of organic farming methods.

Research results were supported from previous studies that farmers' adoption of organic farming is influenced by various factors. Education, income, and access to information are positively associated with knowledge of organic practices (Sapbamrer & Thammachai, 2021; Karipidis & Karypidou, 2021). However, knowledge alone may not drive behavioral changes, as evidenced by the attitude-behavior gap observed among conventional farmers (Luh et al., 2023).

Factors such as farm characteristics, economic incentives, and policy support also play crucial roles in adoption decisions (Karipidis & Karypidou, 2021; Luh et al., 2023). Personal capabilities and contextual factors contribute to the persistence of unsustainable farming practices among conventional farmers (Luh et al., 2023).

In Ghana, farmers' attitudes towards organic fertilizer practices are generally weak, with education, resource endowment, and access to extension services being key influencing factors (Daadi & Latacz-Lohmann, 2021). To promote organic farming adoption, targeted interventions, training programs, and policy support are necessary to bridge the gap between knowledge and practice (Sapbamrer & Thammachai, 2021; Daadi & Latacz-Lohmann, 2021).

Table 4: Computed Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient between the farmers' knowledge, attitude, and organic farming practices and the selected characteristics of the respondents

Selected Characteristics	Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (ρ)		
	Knowledge	Attitude	Practice
Age	-.072	.117	-.003
Educational Attainment	.267*	-.134	.016
Farming Experience	-.042	-.017	-.037
Organic Farming Experience	.049	-.011	.036
Farm Size	-.138	.120	-.060
Monthly Income	.237*	-.174	.040

** Correlation is significant at the 1% level (2-tailed); * Correlation is significant at the 5% level (2-tailed)

Organic farming provides farmers with various opportunities to increase their income, including higher pricing, cost savings, increased market access, products with value, greater yield stability, lower market risks, and access to support programs. Farmers may improve their economic sustainability and achieve long-term revenue development by implementing organic methods and capitalizing on the rising demand for organic products.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

The Organic Agriculture Production Extension Project, initiated by the College of Agriculture and Forestry, was designed to enhance the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of coconut farmers in Barangay Sitog, Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte regarding organic agriculture. The evaluation sought to determine the overall effectiveness of the training in promoting sustainable agricultural practices among these farmers. Specifically, the key objectives included assessing the level of knowledge acquired by the beneficiaries, evaluating their attitudes towards organic agriculture, determining the extent to which they have adopted organic farming practices, and analyzing how personal characteristics—such as age, educational attainment, farming experience, organic farming experience, farm size, and monthly income—related to their KAP levels. The results demonstrated a generally high level of knowledge among coconut farmers, with a majority exhibiting a favorable attitude towards organic agriculture. However, the practical application of organic farming practices showed variability, highlighting areas that require further intervention. While the farmers' educational attainment and income were found to have a positive association with their level of knowledge, these factors did not significantly influence their attitudes or the extent to which they applied organic farming practices. This suggests that although farmers possess a sound understanding of organic methods and maintain positive attitudes, translating this knowledge into practice remains challenging due to other underlying factors such as economic stability, access to resources, and logistical barriers. The study's findings underscore the importance of providing more targeted interventions that bridge the gap between knowledge and practical

implementation, ensuring that farmers are equipped not only intellectually but also practically to engage in sustainable farming.

Conclusion

The findings from this study underscore the effectiveness of the Organic Agriculture Production Extension Project in enhancing awareness and fostering positive attitudes towards organic farming among coconut farmers in Barangay Sitog. The high levels of knowledge and positive attitudes among the respondents are indicative of the project's success in educating the community about the benefits of sustainable agricultural practices. Despite these positive outcomes, the study also reveals that practical application remains inconsistent, with only a moderate number of farmers fully adopting organic farming methods. The discrepancy between high knowledge and positive attitudes on the one hand, and limited practical application on the other, points to the presence of barriers that hinder full adoption. These barriers likely include economic challenges, limited availability of organic inputs, and the need for more practical training and demonstrations. The study concludes that while factors such as educational attainment and income have contributed to an increased understanding of organic farming, they alone are insufficient to drive the complete adoption of these practices. The transition from knowledge to practice requires additional targeted support, including hands-on training, access to organic farming resources, and economic incentives. Addressing these challenges is essential for ensuring that farmers not only understand organic agriculture but are also able to effectively implement and sustain these practices. Furthermore, fostering a supportive environment through resource provision, training programs, and policy incentives can significantly enhance the translation of knowledge and attitudes into practical, sustained organic farming activities.

Recommendation

- 1. Enhanced Practical Training Programs:** To bridge the gap between knowledge and practical application, it is essential to conduct more hands-on training sessions for coconut farmers. These training programs should emphasize practical demonstrations and provide farmers with opportunities to practice organic farming techniques in real-world settings. This approach will help to reinforce theoretical knowledge through application, ultimately boosting farmers' confidence and ability to implement organic practices effectively.
- 2. Resource Accessibility and Subsidies:** A major barrier identified in this study is the limited access to organic farming inputs, such as organic fertilizers and pesticides. It is recommended that local government units and agricultural agencies provide subsidies or grants for organic inputs. Making these resources affordable and accessible will reduce the financial burden on farmers, encouraging them to transition from conventional to organic farming practices.
- 3. Strengthening Farmer Cooperatives and Peer Support Networks:** Strengthening the formation of farmer cooperatives or peer support networks can foster collective action and support among farmers. Such cooperatives can facilitate the bulk purchase of organic inputs, making them more affordable, and provide a platform for farmers to share experiences,

challenges, and best practices. This collaborative approach can significantly enhance the adoption of organic farming methods by creating a supportive community environment.

- 4. Targeted Capacity-Building on Soil Health Management:** The study found that soil analysis was one of the least adopted practices. To address this, specific capacity-building workshops focused on soil health management should be conducted. Training farmers on how to assess and improve soil health, including soil testing and the use of organic amendments, will help them understand the critical role of soil quality in sustainable agriculture and encourage more widespread adoption of this practice.
- 5. Economic Incentives and Policy Advocacy:** Advocacy for policy measures that provide economic incentives for organic farmers is crucial. Government programs that offer financial rewards, tax breaks, or certification support for farmers who adopt organic farming can serve as significant motivators. Additionally, integrating organic farming initiatives into broader rural development programs can help create a more supportive economic environment that encourages sustainable practices.
- 6. Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establishing a continuous monitoring and evaluation framework will help track the progress of the organic agriculture extension project and make necessary adjustments based on farmers' feedback. Regular assessments will provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by farmers and the impact of interventions, allowing for timely improvements in the support provided.
- 7. Awareness Campaigns and Education on Long-Term Benefits:** While farmers may have knowledge of organic practices, awareness of the long-term benefits—such as improved soil health, increased resilience to climate change, and enhanced market opportunities for organic produce—can further motivate adoption. Educational campaigns focusing on these long-term benefits should be conducted to strengthen farmers' commitment to transitioning towards organic agriculture.
- 8. Integration of Organic Farming into School Curricula:** To ensure sustainability and future growth of organic farming practices, it is recommended to integrate organic farming concepts into the educational curricula of local schools and agricultural training centers. By educating the next generation about sustainable agriculture, a culture of organic farming can be fostered, ensuring long-term adoption and community resilience.

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Appendix 1

Figure 3: Barangay Hall of Sitog with its logo

Appendix 2

Figure 4: The researcher conducted the face-to-face interviews to the beneficiaries of the OAP project of JMRSU-CAF

Appendix 3

Figure 5: The researcher conducted the focus group discussion to present the evaluation result to the beneficiaries of the project with the barangay councilors and coconut farmers' association officials

Appendix 4

Questionnaire

ORGANIC AGRICULTURE PRODUCTION: KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICES (KAP) OF THE BENEFICIARIES FROM BARANGAY SITOG, KATIPUNAN, ZDN

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

I. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Date Surveyed: _____

1. Name of the Respondent: _____

2. Age: _____

3. Address: _____

4. Gender:

Male

Female

LGBTQ: _____

5. Civil Status:

- | | |
|---|------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Single | <input type="checkbox"/> Widower |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Married | <input type="checkbox"/> Separated |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Widow | <input type="checkbox"/> Annulled |
| <input type="checkbox"/> others please specify: _____ | |

6. Religion affiliation

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Roman Catholic | <input type="checkbox"/> Seventh Day Adventist |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Jehovah's Witnesses | <input type="checkbox"/> Islam |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Iglesia Ni Cristo | <input type="checkbox"/> Pentecostal |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Alliance | <input type="checkbox"/> Others specify: _____ |

7. Ethnic origin

- | | |
|--|----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ilonggo | <input type="checkbox"/> Manobo |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Cebuano | <input type="checkbox"/> Tagalog |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Boholano | <input type="checkbox"/> Subanen |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Others specify: _____ | |

8. Educational Attainment:

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> No Education | <input type="checkbox"/> College Level |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Elementary Level | <input type="checkbox"/> College graduate |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Elementary graduate | <input type="checkbox"/> Post-graduate <input type="checkbox"/> Ms <input type="checkbox"/> PhD |
| <input type="checkbox"/> High School Level | <input type="checkbox"/> Tech-Vocational |
| <input type="checkbox"/> High School graduate | <input type="checkbox"/> Other specify: _____ |

9. Main Occupation:

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Farming | <input type="checkbox"/> Private Employee |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Overseas Filipino Worker | <input type="checkbox"/> Businessman/woman |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gov't Employee | <input type="checkbox"/> Others, pls. specify _____ |

10. Monthly income

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> 0-5,000 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5,001-10,000 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 10,001-15,000 | <input type="checkbox"/> 15,001-20,000 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 20,001-25,000 | <input type="checkbox"/> 25,001-30,000 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 30,001-35,000 | <input type="checkbox"/> 35,001-beyond |

11. Years of farming experience: _____

12. Years of organic farming experience: _____

13. Ownership status of the farmland

owned

rented

inherited

others specify: _____

14. Size of coconut farm area: _____ hectares

15. Are you a member of an organization?

Yes

No

16. Name of Organization:

Farmers' Association

Women's Association

Farmers' Cooperative

Others, pls. specify _____

II. KNOWLEDGE OF THE BENEFICIARIES TO THE OAP EXTENSION PROJECT CONDUCTED BY JRMSU-KC, COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY

In the following item, please ANSWER based on your AWARENESS as to the extension project conducted. Please check the box of your answer: **True** or **False**

Statements	TRUE	FALSE
1. Ang organikong pamaagi sa pag-uma usa kini sa pamaagi aron ma.minusan ang gasto sa abono.		
2. Ang pag-gamit og kemikal sa uma ang usa ka estratihya sa organikong pamaagi sa pag-uma.		
3. Ang pag-spray og kemikal sa atong umahan dili maka-hatag og negatibong epekto sa kinaiyahan.		
4. Ang paghimo og paggamit sa concoction o organic foliar ang usa ka pamaagi sa organikong pag-uma.		
5. Dako og ikatabang ang wati sa pagpatambok sa atong yuta aron modako atong ani.		
6. Ang concoction usab mahimong bitamina sa atong binuhing mga manok, baboy, og uban pang-kahayopan sa umahan		
7. Dapat mauna og aplay ang mga kemikal na pesticide/insecticide usa kita mo-aplay og organikong pesticide sama sa OHN (Oriental Herb Nutrients) sa pagpalayas sa mga dangan.		
8. Ang bani o sapal sa saging ang ibutang sa vermi bed aron modaghan atong mga wati.		
9. Ang bokashi kay usa ka kemikal na abono na pweding makadaot sa atong kinaiyahan, sa ubang tanom, og sa lawas sa tawo.		
10. Ang gulay nga ang giabonohan og organic pwedi nga kanoon og presko og mas masustansya kaysa sa uban nga giabonohan og inorganic nga abono.		

III. ATTITUDE OF THE BENEFICIARIES OF THE OAP EXTENSION PROJECT CONDUCTED BY JRMSU-KC, COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY

Please rate the following statements based on your perception as to their level of understanding. Please use the following rating scale and description:

5- Strongly Agree

4- Agree

3- Uncertain

2- Disagree

1- Strongly Disagree

Positibong Pahayag

Statements	5 (SA)	4 (A)	3 (U)	2 (D)	1 (SD)
1. Importante nga makabalo ta sa organikong pamaagi sa pag-uma					
2. Dali ra himoon ang mga pamaagi nga organiko					
3. Importante kini aron molambo ang pagdako sa mga tanom og hayop					
4. Makatabang kini aron adunay alternatibong pagkakitaan ang mga mag-uuma					
5. Importante kini aron madungagan ang nutrisyon sa yuta					
6. Dili gasto ang paghimo sa pamaagi nga organiko					
7. Dako kini og natabang aron ma-minusan ang gasto sa abono.					
8. Daghan og benepisyo ang makuha sa ing ani nga pamaagi sa pagtanom					
9. Nagmalipayon kami nga nakat-unan namo ang organikong pamaagi sa pag-uma					
10. Nakatahatag kini og paglambo sa kinabuhi namong mag-uuma.					

Negatibong Pahayag

Statements	5 (SA)	4 (A)	3 (U)	2 (D)	1 (SD)
1. Dakong babag sa amoa ang magkat-on ani nga pamaagi					
2. Kinahanglan og dakong kapital sa organikong pamaagi					
3. Kuti himoon ang mga pamaagi sa organik					
4. Gadungag lang kini sa galastuhon sa among panimalay					
5. Walay epektibo kini sa pagpatambok sa yuta					
6. Wala kini makahatag og alternatibong kita sa amoa					
7. Mas nidako ang gasto namo sa abono tungod wala kini epekto sa among pag-uma					
8. Walay benepisyo makuha kini nga pamaagi aron mapalambo ang kinabuhi sa mag-uuma					
9. Nagmahay mi nga niapil mi ani nga pagtulon-an sa organikong pamaagi sa pag-uma					
10. Dili na ko moapil og usan sa training sa organikong pamaagi sap ag-uma					

IV. PRACTICES OF THE BENEFICIARIES OF THE OAP EXTENSION PROJECT CONDUCTED BY JRMSU-KC, COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY

Listed in the table below are the possible practices employed by the farmers on their farms. Please rate the statements as to your perception of the extent of practices you derived from them. Please use the rating and description below; 3 being the highest and 0 as the lowest.

3- Regularly

2- Sometimes

1- Seldom

0- Not at all

Statements	3 (R)	2 (So)	1 (Sc)	0 (N)
1. Nagbutang ako ug tai sa kabaw o manok sa umahan matag panahon				
2. Ang maayo nga pagtikad kay gihimo sa dili pa gi aplayan og abono				
3. Kanunay nga gi-test ang yuta				
4. Ang mga organikong pestisidyo gigamit kauban sa mga manure				
5. Ang mga hayop gitambalan alang sa suplemento sa manure				
6. Ang mga peste o mga insekto kontrolado usab pinaagi sa paggamit sa bag-ong organikong pamaagi sa teknolohiya. E.g. OHN, IPM, og uban pa.				
7. Ang kultibado nga uma gitipigan nga wala pa ang dugang nga pagtikad				
8. Gibisbisan nako ang akong uma kutob sa gikinahanglan				
9. Ang eskedyul sa pagpananom ug ang rotation sa tanom gimintinar sa hustong paagi				
10. Dali ra kong nagtikad ug daghang tanom sa samang yuta.				